
Effects of Animated-Media Strategy on Students' Academic Achievement and Interest in Ecology Concept in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Effects of Animated-Media Strategy on students' Academic Achievement and Interest in Ecology Concept in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental design involving two groups (one experimental and the other control) was used. The population of the study comprised of SSII students in public senior secondary schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State. Two (2) coeducation schools out of 35 were systematically selected. Simple random sampling technique was used to select two schools which comprised of 127 students as the sample size. Two instruments titled Ecology Achievement Test (EAT) and Ecology Interest Questionnaire (EIQ) were used for data collection which were validated by experts, the reliability coefficient of the instruments were determined through PPMC and Cronbach's alpha, which are 0.81 and 0.72 respectively. The result from the study revealed that Biology students taught Ecology using Media animated strategy have higher mean achievement scores than those taught using conventional method, female students performed better than male students in the experimental group, students taught ecology using media animated strategy has more positive impact in interest level than those taught using conventional method of teaching. Finally, female Biology students have higher interest level than their male counterpart in Gumel Education Zone. Based on these findings, it was recommended that Biology Teachers of Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Educational Zone should be encouraged to expose their students to Media animation strategy, as it was found to be effective and gender friendly in this study, Biology teachers should use media animated strategy so as to encourage students' active participation during the teaching and learning process. Measures should be taken in order to prevent differences between different groups while teaching and learning biological concepts.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Animated-Media Strategy, Interest.

Introduction

The development of the modern world in the twenty-first century is heavily reliant on science, technology, and mathematics (STM) (Anaeto & Ugwok 2016). They have changed all facets of human activity, including business, education, health, and agriculture. As a result, countries all around the world are still working to make sure that their science and technology curricula are always improving. By shielding human societies from ignorance, illiteracy, illness, and poverty, science and technology education serve as the cornerstone of sustainable national development (Ahmed, 2013). According to Ogunleye (2016) Science is a dynamic human endeavor that aims to understand how our world functions. This understanding helps man to know more about the nature of universe. Without the application of science, it would have been difficult for man to explore the other planets of the universe. Science comprised the basic disciplines such as Biology, Chemistry, Mathematics, and Physics. Science education is meant to expose the learners to scientific nature (facts, theory, principles and concepts), processes, attitudes and the provide learners with skills of professional scientist (Osokoya, 2013). Science instruction begins in kindergarten and continues through elementary, secondary, and university education. Some courses, including those in medicine, biochemistry, microbiology, zoology, botany, anatomy, and environmental sciences, are based on the knowledge learned in primary school. The goal of science education is to expose students to the abilities of professional scientists. The objectives of the science curriculum as provided in the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) include; adequate laboratory and field skills in science, meaningful and relevant knowledge, ability to apply scientific knowledge to everyday life. Science curriculum has developed a package of animation and multimedia teaching, an indication that science and technology has gone beyond their conventional approaches into the use of animation teaching for schools and colleges. These science subjects comprises of Mathematics Physics Chemistry and Biology.

Biology is the study of living things, including their structure, function, and behaviors, as well as their evolution, distribution, and taxonomy (Adebanjo 2019). The field concerned with all the physiochemical aspects of life. Biology is subdivided into separate branches for convenience of study, though all the subdivisions are interrelated by basic principles. Thus, while it is tradition to separate the study of plants (Botany) from that of animals (Zoology) and the study of the structure of organisms (Morphology) from that of function (Physiology) all living things share in a common certain biological phenomena for example, various means of reproduction, cell division and the transmission of genetic materials (Tafi, 2016). Modern principles of others fields: chemistry, medicine and physics, for example are interrelated with those of biology in areas include biochemistry, biomedicine and biophysics (Oliver & Larson, 2015). Biology is one of the science subjects that secondary school students are offering at the senior levels in the Nigerian secondary schools (FME 2013). Biology is one of the among science subject and a requirement for further learning of a number of science-related professional courses like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, biochemistry, micro-biology etc. (Chernecky & Cynthia, 2018).

The science of ecology mainly involves research as the natural world from many viewpoints using many techniques. Modern ecology depend on heavily experiments, both in laboratory and in field settings. These techniques have proved useful in testing ecological theories and in arriving at practical decisions concerning the management of natural resources. An understanding of ecology is important for the survival of the human species. The populations are increasing rapidly all around the world and the people are in grave harm of outstripping the earth's ability to supply the resource that needed for long term survival. Furthermore, social, economic, and political factors often influence the short term distribution

of resources needed by a specific human population. An understanding of ecology principles can aid us to understand the global and regional consequences of competitions among humans for the scarce natural resources that support our living (Biology Dictionary, 2017).

Even though biology is important and popular with Nigerian students, they have performed poorly at the senior secondary school level (Opara, 2011). Over the years there has been high enrolment of Biology students in secondary schools but interestingly, students' performance has not been encouraging. It is worrisome to note that the performance of these students have continued to deteriorate year after year in Biology despite all stakeholders' efforts. This calls for investigation among the goals of science education, biology curriculum and instruction. The West African Examinations Councils (2019) Annual Reports revealed poor performances of most candidates who took the Senior School Certificate Examination Biology. On the average the percentage failure is higher compared to the percentage rate of pass on Biology. This indicated that students' achievement in Biology in the external examinations is low. The traditional method of teaching biology in secondary schools may be the cause of the low performance of Students in external exams (Ude & Onah 2017; Ezra & Agah, 2019; and Umunnakwe & Isah, 2021).

The traditional/conventional teaching methods often used by teachers in teaching Biology include the lecture/expository method, demonstration and direct instruction etc. Some educators have described these traditional teaching methods as inadequate for teaching biology and other science subjects because they place a greater emphasis on memorization and the transmission and imparting of knowledge (Ibe and Nwosu, 2013; Bilesanmi-Awoderu, Afuwape & Jolaosho, 2017; Okwara, Anyagh and Ikyaan, 2019). As a poor method of teaching biology and other science subjects. The conventional/traditional teaching methods involve unidirectional flow of information/knowledge from teacher to the students and do not encourage process skill acquisition needed for proper understanding of biological principles, concepts and facts. According to Afolabi (2019), one of the reasons why students perform poorly in science classes is the way science is now taught. Many teachers hold lectures and give direct instructions as part of the conventional/traditional teaching technique, which takes place in the classroom.

Therefore, teaching biology ideas requires the use of audio-visual resources (Afolabi, 2019). Computer animation for education has many advantages. Any learning related to instructional computer animation fosters emotional intelligence and entertaining cognitive thinking while offering a stress-free learning environment. Students benefit from instructional computer animation because it offers a unique and captivating presentation of all the data and ideas (Salisu, 2015). Modules helps with instructional computer animation, according to Aminordin (2007) in Salisu (2015), is a useful technique to draw attention and be able to give specific details about how the object moves and changes over time, which can lower the degree of abstract concepts and Students' attention is readily captured, and the material is delivered more effectively.

According to Jamalludin and Zaidatun (2003) in Salisu (2015), the use of instructional computer animation makes it easier to explain a subject or demonstrate a skill, which allows students to employ more senses and resources during learning and keeps their interest and attention for longer.

However, Media-Animated educational strategies make use of animation and cartoon style. It enables the integration of sound and moving images into the lesson, expanding the teacher's

capacity to provide resources that promote student engagement with the curriculum (Dike, 2008).

The use of multimedia-animated instruction reduces the learning task and time; it creates room for consistency and learning mastery by increasing retention, safety and motivation. Learners enjoy interactive learning through cartoon teaching since it is efficient, effective and flexible. It enhances communication and simultaneously stimulates the senses of sight and hearing. It also offers a tangible foundation for understanding abstract ideas, resulting in more lasting and significant learning (Staylor, 2002; Kellerman, 2004). Media animation instructional strategy is a form of instructional method that implies the use of computer animation, graphic and cartoons in classroom instruction. It is the process of taking pictures of successive puppet or model postures or drawings to give the impression that the video is moving when viewed as a sequence (Mayer & Moreno 2012). The scholars further refer animation as a simulated motion picture depicting movement of drawn. Researchers like Ikwuka and Samuel (2017) found that science students exposed to multimedia and computer animation method of instruction had higher interest achievement level and of science concepts taught.

Hence, Aronson (2014) explained academic achievement as the degree of attainment by student in schools, colleges and universities either in class, laboratory, library, project or field work in which the student is sufficiently exposed. Anekwe (2019) sees achievement as a test for the measurement and comparison of skills in various fields of academic study. Hence achievement could be described as a task which has been accomplished successfully, especially by means of exertion, skill practice or perseverance. Researchers (Lawal, 2017; Atadoga, & Lakpini, 2013) found that the persistent low academic achievement in science education is attributed to teacher instructional strategies among others. Thus, instructional strategies used by teachers in teaching learning process have significant influence on learners' academic achievement. In this study, the researcher investigated the effect of Animated-Media instructional strategy on Biology students' academic achievement and interest in ecology concepts of Secondary Schools.

Then, Interest is a sensation that calls attention to something out of curiosity or worry. According to Renninger and Hiddi (2016), curiosity is a crucial cognitive and affective motivating factor that directs focus, promotes learning across a range of subject areas, and grows via experience for all students, regardless of age. According to Aggarwal (2018), the goal of education is to capture and hold students' interest in lessons that involve multiple dimensions of instruction. Students' interest in studying is positively impacted by an engaging teacher, useful teaching resources, and an idle learning atmosphere and procedures, according to Mangal (2020).

According to Neumann, Neumann, and Hood (2011), students show a great deal of interest in using visual instructional resources to solve geographical problems. They have also proposed using instructional resources as a springboard for students' inquiry-based scientific research. Interest is defined as an individual's emotion evoked by a specific item or activity. It indicates that a child will become interested in anything that is deemed appealing or engaging. Accordingly, in a classroom setting, a student will only pay attention to a lesson if the instruction is conveying a desire to the student (Nwachukwu, 2013; Danjuma, 2015). Okeke (2016) states clearly that interest is viewed as a motivational construct in psychological and educational measurement. Salisu (2015) stated that media-animated instructional strategy is significantly more effective in improving students' achievements and interest than the

traditional lecture method. Interest is a crucial component of teaching and learning since motivated students are more likely to do well. When teaching and learning biology, student interest is crucial. This is because when a student becomes interested in an activity, he/she is likely to be more extremely involved in that activity. According to Chuwku (2016), people can show their interest by simply stating what they like and don't like. He also mentioned that improper teaching strategies could be the source of students' lack of interest.

Hence, Gender is also one of the factors influencing students' achievement in biology at senior secondary school levels. Researches have been conducted in the areas of gender-related differences in the academic achievement of students in different areas. Some studies revealed that girls scored significantly higher than boys in science-related subjects (Eze, 2017). Contrary to this, Schodiende (2013) and Onose (2017) in their studies revealed that male students are academically higher than their female counterparts in science. While some studies revealed that there was no significant difference in the performance of boys and girls when taught Geography, Social Studies and Biology (Evrekil, 2015). Gender is a socio-cultural construct that implies the distinct duties and obligations of men and women in a given culture, according to Singh (2016).

The matter of gender in learning spans quite a number of other issues as well. These include differences in perception of visual information by females and males, differences in learning scientific knowledge through computer-based learning materials, differences in academic achievement in science subjects, differences in perceptions, retention and attitudes towards the computer, and differences in level of anxiety towards the use of computers (Butler, 2015; Muncer, 2016; Enochsson, 2017; Madell, Wong & Hanafi, 2017; Aremu, 2018; Isman & Celikli, 2019). It is therefore, beneficial to investigate whether gender of students involved in using media-animated instructional strategy would have an effect on academic achievement and interest in ecology. Looking at the importance of the media-animated strategy in teaching and learning process, but it unfortunately suffers neglect in teaching ecology this is because there is little research conducted using media-animated strategy. It is against this background, this study intends to investigate the effects of media-animated strategy on Students' academic achievement and interest in ecology concept in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In any teaching and learning process, the cardinal objective is to see that the learner performs tasks and if possible transfer the experience in solving problems in a new situation, this objective is hardly being achieved over the years. Considering the uppermost importance of Biology to human life, it has been noted that the achievement of students in internal and external examinations have not been impressive and the failure rate is much higher and worrying. This can be attested to from the results of students in Biology from (2021-2023). Concerning the percentage of biology students failing external exams in recent years may be a result of their weak biology foundation (Nbina & Obomanu, 2016). This may also be connected to the method of teaching used by the science teachers, this may also be related to the teaching methodology employed by science instructors (Sequeira, 2018). This persistent low achievement in Biology process skills acquisition exhibited by science students in practical examination leaves no doubt about the ineffectiveness of the teaching method used by science teachers for teaching this subject. This poor achievement of students in Biology and particularly the ecology concepts is very disheartening and loses confidence. This

observation was confirmed by WAEC Chief Examiner's report on Biology from 2021 – 2023 in Gumel, Jigawa State, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1.1: Performance of Students in Biology at SSCE level from (2021-2023)

Year	No of Students Present	No of Students Pass	% Pass	No of Students Fail	% fail	Total
2021	228953	80355	35	148598	65	100%
2022	250099	86150	34	163949	66	100%
2023	289520	84520	21	205000	79	100%

Source: Jigawa State Educational Resource Department (JERD), (2023).

In view of this, this study seeks to investigate the effects of media animated strategy on students' academic achievement and interest in ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Find out the effect of media animated strategy on students' academic achievement in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.
- ii. Examine the effect of media animated strategy on students' interest in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.
- iii. Determine whether or not there is gender difference on students' academic achievement when taught Ecology using media animated strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.

Research Question

The research questions put forward for the purpose of this study are:

- i. What is the effect of media animated strategy on students' academic achievement in Ecology Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?
- ii. What is the effect of media animated strategy on students' interest in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?
- iii. Is there any difference between male and female students' academic achievement when taught Ecology using media animated strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the significant level of 0.05.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught ecology with media animated strategy and those taught using conventional method of teaching in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in mean interest scores of Biology students taught ecology using media animated strategy and those exposed to conventional method of teaching in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students' taught ecology using media animated strategy in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

Research Design

The design for this study is quasi experimental using pretest and posttest Experimental and control group design. The study used two groups; experimental and control groups. Experimental group (EG) were exposed to experimental treatment (X_1). That is, teaching using animated-media instructional strategy. While, control group (CG) was treated using Conventional method (O_2). The experimental group and control group was pre-tested to ensure group equivalence, thereafter the groups were exposed to treatment for 6 weeks and at the end of which post-test was administered to determine students Achievement and Interest.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the SSII biology students of public schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State. There are thirty-five senior secondary schools, with total population of 27,610 students. Schools in the zone have valid data of SSII students offering biology with a population of 3,300 SSII biology students out of which 2,551 are boy's schools and 749 are from girl's schools with an average of 16 years the population are Homogeneous in nature derived.

Sample Size

A total number of 127 SS II biology students were drawn from two public senior secondary schools of Gumel education zone to form the sample of the study. Subjects were randomly assigned to both experimental and control groups prior to the administration of treatment. Two intact classes (one from experimental group and one from control group) were used for the study. This is because the study design is quasi-experimental. All the public senior secondary schools are not co-education schools. The two schools were systematically selected comprising one experimental and one control as represented by letter G and N for ethical reasons. The two sampled schools were assigned as experimental and control group using random sampling technique and School G serves as Experimental school and school N serves as Control school respectively.

Table 2: Showing the Sample Size of the Experimental and control groups in SSII

S/N	Schools	Male	Female	Total
1	School G (Experimental Group)	29	38	67
2	School N (Control Group)	28	32	60
	Total	57	70	127

Instrumentation

Two instruments were used for data collection which are Ecology Achievement Test (EAT) and Ecology Interest Questionnaire (EIQ). Ecology Achievement Test (EAT) adapted from WASCCE (2021-2023) question papers on ecology with different section, initially 40 items were developed but during pretest/pilot study 10 items were left unanswered even with the validation from expert reducing it to 30 items. The two instruments were validated by experts. The reliability of EAT was found via PPMCC to be 0.72 and that of BIQ was found using the Cronbach's Alpha as 0.83.

In this chapter, data collected is analyzed and presented under the following sub-headings: result of the findings and lastly discussion of the findings. The data collected in the course of study were analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version

20.0. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions and analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results are presented in tables in line with the research questions raised, and the corresponding formulated hypothesis.

Research Questions One: What is the effect of media animated strategy on students' academic achievement in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviations Scores of Students' Academic Achievement in Experimental and Control Groups.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Diff.	Remarks
MAS	Experimental	67	65.72	11.562	19.35	High
CLM	Control	60	46.37	10.659		

Table 3 shows the mean score and standard deviation of students taught Ecology using Media Animated Strategy (MAS) and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method (CLM). The results show that the mean achievement scores for experimental group is (M=65.72; SD=11.56) and for control group is (M=46.37; SD=10.65) respectively. And the mean difference was 19.35 in favour of experimental group. This implies that animated-media strategy is effective in enhancing student's academic achievement in Ecology in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught ecology with media animated strategy and those taught using conventional method of teaching in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

Table 4: ANCOVA test for the Posttest Scores of Biology Students taught Ecology using Media Animated Strategy and those taught using Conventional Method of Teaching.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Decision
Corrected Model	251.815 ^a	2	125.907	17.599	.000	.221	
Intercept	668.717	1	668.717	93.473	.000	.430	
Pretest	21.315	1	21.315	2.979	.087	.023	
Group	205.412	1	205.412	28.712	.000	.188	Rejected
Error	887.114	124	7.154				
Total	46872.000	127					
Corrected Total	1138.929	126					

a. R Squared = .221 (Adjusted R Squared = .209)

Table 4 reveals the ANCOVA analyses for the biology students taught using conventional method and those taught ecology using media animated strategy. The F calculated value variable (Achievement-group) is 28.712 with the significant level of P at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 therefore; the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Biology students taught ecology with media animated strategy and

those taught using conventional method of teaching in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state, (F-cal = 28.712, P=0.000<0.05).

Research Question Two: What is the effect of media animated strategy on students' interest in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviations Scores of Students' Interest in Experimental and Control Groups.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Diff.	Remarks
MAS	Experimental	67	74.87	15.13	21.89	high
CLM	Control	60	52.98	13.59		

The result in table 4 revealed that the mean interest score for students in experimental group was (M=74.87; SD=15.13) and that of control group was (M=52.98; SD=13.59) with mean difference of 21.89 in favour of students in experimental group after the posttest administration. This implies that students in experimental group developed higher interest in ecology concepts than that of control group as revealed in the mean difference score. Hence, Media Animated Strategy (MAS) has a positive impact in generating students' interest towards learning ecology concepts in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant difference in mean interest scores of Biology students taught ecology using media animated strategy and those exposed to conventional method of teaching in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

Table 5: ANCOVA test for the Posttest Interest Scores of Control and Experimental Groups.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Decision
Corrected Model	3902.151 ^a	2	1951.075	17.400	.000	.219	
Intercept	8525.956	1	8525.956	76.037	.000	.380	
Pre_interest	123.520	1	123.520	1.102	.296	.009	Accepted
Group	3901.846	1	3901.846	34.798	.000	.219	
Error	13903.959	124	112.129				
Total	454951.000	127					
Corrected Total	17806.110	126					

a. R Squared = .219 (Adjusted R Squared = .207)

Table 5 reveals the ANCOVA analyses for interest level of Biology students taught using conventional method and those exposed to media animated strategy. The F calculated value variable (Interest- Group) is 34.798 with the significant level of P at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 therefore; the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference in interest level on ecology students taught using media using media animated strategy and those exposed to conventional method of teaching in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state, in favour of the experimental group, (F-cal = 34.798, P=0.000<0.05).

Research Question Three: Is there any difference between male and female students' academic achievement when taught Ecology using media animated strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State?

Table 6: Difference between the Mean Academic Achievement Scores of Male and Female

SS II Biology Students using Experimental Group

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Diff.	Remarks
Gender	Male	29	16.64	3.76	3.61 students	Difference exist in favour of female
	Female	38	20.25	1.64		

Table 6 presents the mean scores and standard deviations of male and female Biology students on the effects of animated media strategy on academic achievement in senior secondary school Ecology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state. The results show that the mean achievement scores for male students is (M=16.64; SD=3.76) and for female students is (M=20.25; SD=1.64) respectively. And the mean difference was 3.61 in favour of female students. By implication the results clearly showed that female students performed significantly better than male students when taught Ecology using animated media strategy.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students' taught ecology using media animated strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state.

Table 7: ANCOVA test for the Posttest Scores of Male and Female Biology Students taught Ecology using Media Animated Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	EtaDecision
Corrected Model	194.947 ^a	2	97.474	11.928	.000	.295	
Intercept	470.149	1	470.149	57.534	.000	.502	
Pretest	.643	1	.643	.079	.780	.001	
Gender	191.720	1	191.720	23.461	.000	.292	Rejected
Error	465.786	57	8.172				
Total	21344.000	60					
Corrected Total	660.733	59					

a. R Squared = .295 (Adjusted R Squared = .270)

Table 7 reveals the ANCOVA analyses for male and female Biology students taught ecology using media animated strategy. The F calculated value variable (Gender) is 23.461 with the significant level of P at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 therefore; the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level (0.05). Hence, there is significant mean difference between male and female students' academic achievement taught ecology using media animated strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa state. (F-cal = 23.461, P=0.000<0.05).

Discussion of Findings

The result from the findings revealed no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught using media animated strategy and those taught using conventional method in favor of experimental group. The result of the ANCOVA test result on the mean academic achievement scores of Secondary School students exposed to media animated teaching strategy on ecology and those taught with conventional method revealed a significant difference in favor of students taught with media animated strategy (experimental group). This indicated that exposing students to media animated instructional strategy have understood the concept of ecology more easily than those exposed to Conventional Method. Therefore, the findings from this study in respect of the research question one and hypothesis one (H_{01}) agreed with previous findings reported by other investigators such as; Yaki (2011), Bulut, Ercan and Bilen (2013), Thomas and Israel (2014), Salisu (2015), Nungwo (2017), Aiyedun, Tope and Gloria (2020), Anekwe, Christopher, Ejike and Opara (2021) and Ola, Onoja, Isiyaku & Bala (2022), whose in their individuals studies discovered that animated media strategy enhancing and facilitating clear understanding of concepts in different subject areas. The finding also concur with the findings of Amal and Samar (2018) who investigated the effects of computer animation strategy on biology academic achievement among students of the faculty of education sciences UNRW turkey and found that students taught with animation have higher achievement in biology than those taught with the conventional method.

The result in respect also indicated a significant difference in the interest scores of students taught using media teaching strategy and conventional teaching methods in favor of media animated strategy. This finding agreed with the earlier findings of Anekwe, Christopher Ejike & Opara (2021). Similarly, the finding is in line with the studies of Egbutu and Okoli (2021) who investigated the effects of the use of computer animation and inquiry method on chemistry students' interest in Onitsha Education Zone of Anambra state and found that the students that were taught chemistry using computer animation and inquiry method had significant effects on students' interest in chemistry. It indicated that computer animation was more effective than inquiry method in improving the interest of students in chemistry. The finding also is in line with Aiyedun, Tope & Gloria (2022) who investigated the effect of Animation teaching strategy on secondary school students academic achievement and interest in climate change in Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria, and the results indicated that higher in students taught climate change using media Animated Strategy than those taught using conventional method.

It was also found from the study that there is significant difference in the achievement of male and female students exposed to media animated teaching strategy. The female students have a higher academic achievement than the male students. The findings showed that female had achieved significantly higher when taught with media animated teaching strategy than their male counterpart. This finding is in line with the findings of Egbunonu (2012) on the Effect of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) on secondary school students' cognitive achievement and interest in Ecological concepts in Aguata Educational zone in Anambra state. The result also revealed media Assisted Instruction had statistical significant difference on female students' achievement, but there was a statistical significant difference on students' interest due to gender. The result also corresponds with that of Yaki (2011) who report a significant difference in academic achievement of male and female students taught ecological concepts using computer animation in secondary schools in Minna, Niger state in favour of female students. This finding is in disparity with the study of Solowale and Folade (2016) revealed that no significant difference existed between the male and female students in

the experimental group taught using computer animated instruction package (CAIP). They observed non-significant difference in the achievement of male and female students in the experimental group could be attributed to the fact that the use of multimedia integrated instruction equally enhanced the achievement of the male and female students. All the students irrespective of their gender were carried along during the lesson, thus, the uniform performance. Similar observation was made in respect of male and female students in the control group. No significant difference was also found to exist between the achievement of male and female students taught ecological concepts using demonstration method. The finding of the study also contradicts that of Oriaklin and Igbudu (2015) that there was gender difference in academic achievement of students in favour of male students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

- i. That animated-media strategy is effective in enhancing student's academic achievement in Ecology in Gumel Education Zone of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
- ii. Animated-media strategy has a positive impact in generating students' interest towards learning ecology concepts in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.
- iii. Female students performed significantly better than male students when taught Ecology using animated media strategy in Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State.

Contributions to Knowledge

The results of this study provided the following contributions to knowledge:

- i. The study established that animated media strategy improves students' academic achievement in ecology concept.
- ii. The study also established that the animated media strategy improves student's interest towards ecology concept.
- iii. The study also established that the animated media strategy is not gender friendly, because female have higher mean achievement scores than the male counterparts. Hence, there is need to give both males and females equal chance to learn and interact with instructional materials.
- iv. Ecology Achievement Test (EAT) was developed by the researcher for this study and it was found to be effective in improving and enhancing students' academic achievement in Ecological concepts of Biology Education in Secondary Schools.
- v. The researcher developed animated-media strategy flow-charts in teaching ecology concept and is unique in the field of Biology Education at senior secondary school level.
- vi. The researcher developed a comprehensive lesson plans package for using Animated Media Strategy, which was new in the field of Biology Education.

Recommendations from the Study

The recommendations from the study are as follows:

- i. Biology teachers should use media animated strategy so as to encourage students' active participation during the teaching and learning procedure.
- ii. Teachers should try as much as possible to guide their students in developing their interest towards learning of Biology through the use innovative teaching strategies such as Animated-Media Strategy.

- iii. Since it was discovered animated media strategy is not gender friendly in teaching Ecology, measures should be taken in order to prevent differences between different groups while teaching and learning of Biology.

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